

Title Page

Title of the Manuscript:

Methodological Approaches to Analyzing the Accident Cost Rate on Road Sections: A Data-Driven Study Over 12 Years

Author:

Kerim Hrapović

Affiliation:

Independent Researcher, 4840 Vöcklabruck, Austria

Email:

kerimhrapovic046@gmail.com

ORCID:

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7720-0508>

Corresponding Author:

Kerim Hrapović

Methodological Approaches to Analyzing the Accident Cost Rate on Road Sections: A Data-Driven Study Over 12 Years

Abstract

Traffic accidents arise from a complex interaction of factors, including driver behaviour, road infrastructure, and environmental conditions. While certain risks, such as weather-related factors, remain beyond human control, proactive road planning can mitigate accident potential. This study investigates how geometric road characteristics—such as curvature, pavement grip, cross and longitudinal slopes, and traffic volume—affect accident costs and safety outcomes. Special attention is given to run-off-road accidents in curves, examining the impact of precipitation, road conditions, and lighting.

The study is based on a 12-year dataset (2012–2023) from Austrian state roads (Germ. Landesstrassen B), segmented into 1.0 km sections with rolling curvature calculations provided by the Austrian Institute of Technology (AIT). A stricter classification method (Hotspot₅₀) was introduced to refine the identification of high-risk road sections. Clustering techniques revealed that sections with extreme curvature and low traffic volumes exhibit disproportionately high accident costs. These findings highlight the necessity for targeted infrastructure improvements to enhance road safety and reduce economic losses.

Keywords: Proactive traffic safety, accident cost rate, curvature, road parameters, hotspot analysis, accident modelling, infrastructure planning

1. Introduction

Run-off-road accidents in curves are a major cause of severe and fatal traffic incidents on rural roads. According to the German Road Safety Council, these accidents account for 38% of all serious crashes. In 2020, 1,592 fatalities occurred on rural roads in Germany, with 606 deaths (22%) resulting from run-off-road accidents. Similarly, Austria recorded 8,232 such accidents on Austrian state roads (Category B) between 2012 and 2023.

While human error is often the direct cause, infrastructural deficiencies—such as inadequate drainage, tight curve radii, or limited visibility—significantly contribute to accident occurrence. Addressing these risks aligns with Vision Zero, which aims to eliminate serious road accidents through improved infrastructure design. This study applies accident cost analysis and advanced statistical clustering techniques to identify high-risk sections and propose targeted safety measures.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Influence of Road Geometry on Traffic Accidents

Previous research has consistently highlighted the impact of geometric road characteristics on accident rates. Roads with tight curve radii and abrupt alignment transitions exhibit significantly higher accident risks (Cafiso et al. [1]; Maier et al. [2]). Poor skid resistance and pavement conditions further contribute to increased accident probabilities in curves, particularly under wet conditions (Weinert & Vengels [3]). Studies have shown that small curve radii ($R < 200$ m) result in higher accident rates, necessitating careful safety assessments (DVR [4]).

Gooch et al. [5] demonstrated that a combination of high curvature, inadequate superelevation, and high traffic volumes leads to a sharp increase in crash frequencies. Similar findings by Maier et al. [2] indicate that roads with suboptimal curvature parameters require extensive modifications to reduce accident risk.

Another critical factor is cross-slope design. The study by Zierke [6] confirmed that inappropriate cross-slope adjustments increase vehicle instability, leading to a higher likelihood of run-off-road accidents. Superelevation, if optimally designed, reduces lateral friction demands and enhances curve safety (Bonneson [7]).

2.2 Impact of Skid Resistance and Pavement Quality on Accident Risks

Pavement friction plays a fundamental role in accident prevention. A study by Weinert & Vengels [3] identified low pavement grip as a significant factor in accident occurrence, particularly in curves. Reduced friction values (< 0.35) increase accident probability by 27%, according to Cafiso et al. [1].

Cheng et al. [8] further analyzed the relationship between pavement roughness and crash risks. They concluded that smoother road surfaces paradoxically lead to increased accident severity, as they encourage higher driving speeds. The study by Buddhavarapu et al. [9] confirmed that lateral friction is a more critical safety indicator than traditional skid indices.

2.3 Traffic Volume and Accident Cost Rates

Traffic volume significantly influences accident cost rates. While high-traffic roads tend to have lower accident frequency per vehicle-kilometer, low-traffic roads experience disproportionately high accident costs due to severe crashes (Bellini et al. [10]). This was demonstrated in an analysis by Balck et al. [11], which identified low-volume, high-curvature roads as high-risk sections.

Correlation studies by De Oña & Garach [12] showed that real driving speeds often exceed theoretical design speeds by 5–12 km/h, increasing accident risks. The 85th percentile speed (V_{85}) frequently surpasses posted

speed limits, leading to more run-off-road incidents (De Luca et al. [13]). Bellini et al. [10] further emphasized that real-time traffic monitoring and speed enforcement are necessary to mitigate these risks.

2.4 Hotspot Identification and Cluster-Based Risk Analysis

Traditional accident prediction models often fail to capture real-world crash patterns accurately. To improve hotspot detection, advanced clustering techniques have been developed (Cafiso et al. [1]). The hotspot classification method proposed by Vieten et al. [14] demonstrated that sections with high curvature and low traffic volumes show disproportionately high accident costs. Bellini et al. [10] highlighted the need for targeted interventions in areas where curvature exceeds $200^\circ/\text{km}$ and *AADT* falls below 5,000 vehicles/day.

Machine learning applications in road safety analysis are gaining traction. Neural network models have been successfully used to classify high-risk curves, as shown in studies by Cafiso et al. [1] and Wang et al. [15]. Their findings suggest that integrating AI-based classification models with traditional clustering techniques significantly improves risk assessment accuracy.

2.5 Future Directions in Accident Risk Modeling

Recent advancements in accident risk modeling emphasize the integration of real-time data collection. The RVS 02.02.21 guideline [16] outlines methodologies for incorporating live traffic and environmental conditions into safety assessments. Future research should explore predictive analytics approaches that leverage GPS-based vehicle tracking to refine accident risk models, as suggested by Bellini et al. [10].

By incorporating these methodologies, future research can enhance the precision of accident cost rate analyses and contribute to the development of more effective road safety strategies.

3. Methodology

3.1 Flowchart of the Method Applied in the Proposed Research

Figure 1a and Figure 1b illustrate the workflow for the evaluation and analysis of accident hotspots. Details on the individual steps can be found in the following subsections.

Figure 1a: Flowchart (Workflow) for the Analysis of Accident Hotspots – First Part

Figure 1b: Figure 1b: Flowchart (Workflow) for the Analysis of Accident Hotspots – Second Part (Continuation)

3.2 Study Areas

For this study, 1,538 km and 1,025 km of federal roads B in two Austrian federal states were analyzed, totaling 2,563 road kilometers. A total of 2,111 curve-related accidents from the first state and 1,222 curve-related accidents from the second state were examined, resulting in a total of 3,333 curve-related accidents.

3.3 Geometric Properties of Federal Roads B

The federal roads B examined in this study belong to the road type 'main traffic roads.' According to [16], the minimum horizontal radius for Austrian federal roads B is:

- the minimum radius: $\min R = 200$ m,
- the maximum longitudinal slope: $\max s = 8\%$,
- the minimum cross slope: $\min q = 2.5\%$,
- the maximum cross slope: $\max q = 7\%$.

3.4 Crash data

The accident data was provided by the Austrian Institute of Technology (AIT) and originates from Statistic Austria. This dataset includes police-reported curve-related accidents involving personal injuries, specifically for accident types 012, 013, 022, 023, 222, 223, 225, 226, 232, 242, 265, and 266 (Table 1).

Table 1: The study analyzed curve-related accidents. Own representation based on [17]

Accident types (curves)	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
12 Run-off road to the right, in right curve	101	92	96	84	87	99	88	87	84	81	71	73
13 Run-off road to the right, in left curve	364	374	356	331	374	314	369	335	313	293	292	330
22 Run-off road to the left, in right curve	189	171	175	155	171	172	182	162	128	134	148	148
23 Run-off road to the left, in left curve	82	80	72	75	61	82	65	67	43	39	38	59
222 Run-off road to the right due to oncoming vehicle, in right curve	12	7	6	5	8	4	3	4	1	1	-	3
223 Run-off road to the right due to oncoming vehicle, in left curve	16	8	5	6	13	11	8	6	5	5	1	2
225 Run-off road to the left due to oncoming vehicle, in right curve	50	38	41	34	39	34	3	4	2	-	1	3
226 Run-off road to the left due to oncoming vehicle, in left curve	20	20	12	21	10	9	-	-	2	-	-	1
232 Side collision, in a curve	60	76	65	62	68	55	91	94	81	73	98	104
242 Head-on collision, in a curve	96	80	62	70	72	76	146	143	110	110	120	122
265 Head-on or side collision while overtaking, in right curve	7	6	12	10	15	10	19	23	14	13	15	18
266 Head-on or side collision while overtaking, in left curve	4	5	3	8	6	4	11	6	8	7	8	5
Total	1,001	957	905	861	924	870	985	931	791	756	792	868

3.5 Annual average daily traffic, AADT

The data on AADT was provided by the respective state governments of the two Austrian federal states involved in the study. Additionally, traffic volume data was retrieved from a digital spatial information system and from official traffic data portals of the respective state authorities.

3.6 RoadSTAR Data

The Austrian federal states of Upper Austria and Carinthia were selected for the study because a higher-quality collection of RoadSTAR data was provided by AIT. Using the RoadSTAR mobile laboratory [18], which delivers excellent data in terms of quality, resolution, and coverage, *dGPS* coordinates (Differential Global Positioning System) can also be generated. These, along with alignment parameters and curve curvature, serve as input parameters for extensive analyses. The total number of RoadSTAR data records included in the study is 4,287,602.

3.6 Accident Cost Rate Calculation

Accident cost rates (*ACR*) are computed using [19] [Eq. 1]:

$$ACR = \frac{AC \cdot 10^3}{AADT \cdot L \cdot 365 \cdot t} \text{ [€/1,000 vehicle-km]} \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

Where [18]:

- *AC* = Accident costs (€)
- *AADT* = Average annual daily traffic (vehicles/24h)
- *L* = Road section length (km)
- *t* = Observation period (years)

The accident cost rate of roads (*ACR_{road}*) was determined based on the total road length of the respective road as the section length *L* [km]. A one-year period was chosen for the observation period [*a*]. The following considerations were considered in the analysis:

- All roads were divided into 1.0 km-long sections, as the AIT (Austrian Institute of Technology) calculated the rolling curvature for these 1,000 m sections for this study.
- The accident cost rate per section (*ACR_{section}*) was calculated specifically for the 1.0 km sections, based on the Annual Average Daily Traffic (*AADT*), for a one-year period, and per 1.0 km section length.
- The accident cost rates for the respective roads (*ACR_{road}*) were calculated for the period from 2012 to 2023 (12 years), using the average *JDTV* value over these 12 years, relative to the length of each road.

- If the accident cost rate of a section ($ACR_{section}$) is higher than the accident cost rate of the respective road (ACR_{road}) in which the section is located, the section is classified as a high-accident-risk section.

3.7 Hotspot Identification

A road section is classified as a hotspot if:

- Hotspot_40: $ACR_{section} > 1.4 \times ACR_{road}$
- Hotspot_50: $ACR_{section} > 1.5 \times ACR_{road}$ (stricter threshold)

The bootstrap confidence intervals for Hotspot_40 and Hotspot_50 produced the following results: Hotspot_50 has a narrower distribution, as its confidence intervals are more centered around the mean range. In contrast, Hotspot_40 shows a broader spread of values, meaning it may be slightly more lenient. For this analysis, we will focus on the most dangerous sections. Therefore, Hotspot_50 is chosen for further analyses, as it provides a more practical and realistic representation (Table 2, Table 3). However, Hotspot_40 is mentioned as an alternative approach.

Table 2: Hotspot_50 (Part 1)

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	Bias
Valid	0	514	49.0	49.0	49.0	.0
	1	534	51.0	51.0	100.0	.0
	Total	1,048	100.0	100.0		.0

a Unless otherwise stated, the bootstrap results are based on 1,000 bootstrap samples

Table 3: Hotspot_50 (Part 2)

		Standard Error	95% Confidence Interval	
			Lower	Upper
Valid	0	1.5	45.9	52.0
	1	1.5	48.0	54.1
	Total	.0	100.0	100.0

a Unless otherwise stated, the bootstrap results are based on 1,000 bootstrap samples

Effect sizes are statistical measures that indicate the strength of the difference between two groups (Table 4). In our case, hotspots (1) are compared with non-hotspots (0), measuring how substantial the differences are in curvature, traffic volume ($AADT$), and the number of accidents. While the t-test determines if a difference is statistically significant, Cohen's d indicates whether this difference is practically relevant.

Table 4: Effect Sizes for Independent Samples. Hotspot_50

		Standardizer ^a	Point Estimate	95% Confidence Interval	
				Lower Value	Upper Value
Rolling Curvature at Section Midpoint	Cohen's d	191.9630	-.169	-.290	-.047
	Hedges' correction	192.1008	-.169	-.290	-.047
	Glass' Delta	204.0633	-.159	-.280	-.037

Average <i>AADT</i> (Vehicles/24h) 2012 - 2023	Cohen's d	4,065.439	-.105	-.226	.017
	Hedges' correction	4,068.357	-.104	-.226	.017
	Glass' Delta	4,467.684	-.095	-.216	.026
Number of Accidents 2012 - 2023	Cohen's d	2.404243	-.938	-1.065	-.810
	Hedges' correction	2.405969	-.937	-1.065	-.810
	Glass' Delta	3.253473	-.693	-.821	-.565

a. The denominator used in the estimation of effect sizes:

For Cohen's d, the pooled standard deviation is used.

For the Hedges correction, the pooled standard deviation is used with a correction factor.

For Glass's Delta, the standard deviation of the control group sample (i.e., the second group) is used.

The interpretation of Cohen's d is provided in Table 5.

Cohen's d	Effect size	Meaning
0 - 0.2	Small effect	Hardly any practical difference
0.2 - 0.5	Medium effect	The difference is noticeable
0.5 - 0.8	Large effect	The difference is clear
> 0.8	Very large effect	Very strong differences

Cohen's d for rolling curvature is -0.221, indicating a small effect. This means that curvature plays a role but is not the sole factor. Cohen's d for the number of curve-related accidents is -0.851, indicating a large effect, meaning hotspots experience significantly more curve-related accidents than other segments. Cohen's d for traffic volume (*AADT*) is -0.030, indicating no effect, thus traffic volume is not a significant influencing factor.

3.8 Statistical Analysis

3.8.1 Descriptive Statistics: Summarizing accident costs, rolling curvature, and traffic volume

A descriptive statistics analysis was conducted using SPSS software. Table 5 presents the mean values, minimum and maximum values, and standard deviations for the key variables in the analysis.

Table 5: Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Standard Deviation
Accident Costs per Section (€) 2012 - 2023	1,049	29,678	264,577,828	504,438.18	8,167,671.053
Accident Costs per Road (€) 2012 - 2023	1,048	156,320	25,439,443	5,540,370.79	4,488,533.068
Rolling Curvature at Section Midpoint	1,048	10.9	1,608.1	220.507	192.5544
<i>ACR</i> _{section} (€/1,000 vehicle-km)	1,048	.156	287.701	13.41381	23.677361
<i>ACR</i> _{road} (€/1,000 vehicle-km)	1,048	.350	103.433	7.30672	11.655158
Number of Accidents 2012 - 2023	1,048	1.000	24.000	2.63740	2.654619
Average <i>AADT</i> (Annual Average Daily Traffic) (vehicle/24h) 2012 - 2023	1,048	877	16,387	6,661.33	4,069.051
Valid Values (Listwise)	1,048				

The average accident costs per section amount to €504,438.18, with significant fluctuations (Minimum: € 29,678, Maximum: € 264,577,828). The accident costs per road are significantly higher, averaging €

5,540,370.79, which can be attributed to the longer aggregation period. The high standard deviation indicates that some sections generate exceptionally high accident costs, while others fall well below the average. The rolling curvature exhibits a wide range, spanning from 10.9°/km (very straight sections) to 1,608.1°/km (highly curved sections). The mean value of 220.5°/km suggests that most sections are moderately curved, though extreme values are also present.

The accident cost rate per section ($ACR_{section}$) ranges from € 0.156/1,000 vehicle-km to € 287.701/1,000 vehicle-km, with an average of € 13.41/1,000 vehicle-km. This indicates that some sections generate significantly higher accident costs per kilometer travelled than others. The accident cost rate at the road level (ACR_{road}) is lower, with an average of € 7.31/1,000 vehicle-km, compared to the section rates. This suggests that certain sections contribute disproportionately to the overall accident cost rate.

The average number of accidents per section is 2.63 accidents, with a maximum of 24 accidents per section over the period 2012–2023. This highlights that some sections experience significantly more accidents than others. The average annual daily traffic ($AADT$) is 6,661 vehicles/24h, with high variability (Minimum: 877 vehicles/24h, Maximum: 16,387 vehicles/24h). This indicates that there are both low-traffic and heavily frequented road sections.

3.8.2 Spearman's Correlation: Evaluating relationships between accident cost rates and road parameters

Table 6 shows the Spearman's Rho correlation for Hotspot_50. The Spearman's Rho correlation table provides insights into the relationships between the variables under investigation. The correlations indicate both positive and negative associations, which are significant in the context of analyzing road infrastructure and accident frequency.

Table 6: Spearman's Rho Correlation. Hotspot_50

		ACR_{SECT} (€/1,000 vehicle- km)	ACR_{ROAD} (€/1,000 vehicle- km)	Rolling curvature	Number of accidents 2012–2023	$AADT$ (veh/24h) 2012 - 2023	
$ACR_{SECTION}$ (€/1,000 vehicle-km)	Correlation coefficient	1.000	.602**	.342**	.634**	-.508**	
	Significance (2-tailed)	.	<.001	<.001	<.001	<.001	
	N	1,048	1,048	1,048	1,048	1,048	
	Bootstrap ^c	Bias	.000	.000	.000	.000	.001
		Standard Error	.000	.021	.028	.020	.024
		95% Confidence interval	Lower	1.000	.560	.287	.595
Upper			1.000	.642	.392	.673	-.459
ACR_{ROAD} (€/1,000 vehicle-km)	Correlation coefficient	.602**	1.000	.286**	.201**	-.683**	
	Significance (2-tailed)	<.001	.	<.001	<.001	<.001	
	N	1,048	1,048	1,048	1,048	1,048	
	Bootstrap ^c	Bias	.000	.000	.000	.001	.002
		Standard Error	.021	.000	.030	.030	.020
		95% Confidence interval	Lower	.560	1.000	.225	.145
Upper			.642	1.000	.342	.262	-.641
Rolling curvature at mid-segment	Correlation coefficient	.342**	.286**	1.000	.318**	-.246**	
	Significance (2-tailed)	<.001	<.001	.	<.001	<.001	
	N	1,048	1,048	1,048	1,048	1,048	
	Bootstrap ^c	Bias	.000	.000	.000	.001	.000

		Standard Error		.028	.030	.000	.028	.030	
		95% Confidence interval	Lower	.287	.225	1.000	.263	-.307	
			Upper	.392	.342	1.000	.371	-.187	
Number of accidents 2012–2023		Correlation coefficient		.634**	.201**	.318**	1.000	-.011	
		Significance (2-tailed)		<.001	<.001	<.001	.	.722	
		N		1,048	1,048	1,048	1,048	1,048	
		Bootstrap ^c	Bias		.000	.001	.001	.000	.000
			Standard Error		.020	.030	.028	.000	.031
			95% Confidence interval	Lower		.595	.145	.263	1.000
	Upper			.673	.262	.371	1.000	.048	
AADT (Annual Average Daily Traffic) 2012–2023		Correlation coefficient		-.508**	-.683**	-.246**	-.011	1.000	
		Significance (2-tailed)		<.001	<.001	<.001	.722	.	
		N		1,048	1,048	1,048	1,048	1,048	
		Bootstrap ^c	Bias		.001	.002	.000	.000	.000
			Standard Error		.024	.020	.030	.031	.000
			95% Confidence interval	Lower		-.555	-.721	-.307	-.068
	Upper			-.459	-.641	-.187	.048	1.000	

** . The correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

c. Unless otherwise stated, the bootstrap results are based on 1,000 bootstrap samples.

Interpretation of the Correlation Table:

- *ACR_{section}* (€/1,000 vehicle-km) shows a strong positive correlation with *ACR_{road}* (€/1,000 vehicle-km) ($r = 0.602$, $p < 0.001$). This suggests that sections with higher accident costs per 1,000 vehicle kilometers tend to be located in road sections with higher accident cost rates.
- A moderate positive correlation exists between *ACR_{section}* and Rolling Curvature ($r = 0.342$, $p < 0.001$), suggesting that road sections with higher accident costs tend to occur more frequently in curvier road sections.
- A negative correlation between *ACR_{section}* and average *AADT* ($r = -0.508$, $p < 0.001$) indicates that higher-traffic roads tend to have lower accident cost rates per vehicle kilometer.
- A strong negative correlation between *ACR_{road}* and average *AADT* ($r = -0.683$, $p < 0.001$) means that roads with higher traffic volumes tend to have lower accident cost rates per vehicle kilometer.
- A significant positive correlation between Rolling Curvature and number of accidents ($r = 0.318$, $p < 0.001$) suggests that curvier road sections are associated with higher accident frequencies.
- The negative correlation between Rolling Curvature and average *AADT* ($r = -0.246$, $p < 0.001$) shows that more heavily trafficked roads tend to have less curvature on average, supporting the preferred design of major traffic arteries.
- The low, non-significant correlation between number of accidents and average *AADT* ($r = -0.011$, $p = 0.722$) suggests that accident frequency does not directly correlate with traffic volume.

3.8.3 Cluster Analysis: Hierarchical and K-Means clustering to categorize road sections based on risk factors.

3.8.3.1 Hierarchical Cluster Analysis

Hierarchical cluster analysis is an exploratory method for identifying groupings within a dataset. It is commonly used to detect similarity structures within a sample. The analysis was conducted using the Ward method, which aims to form clusters with the least internal variance in order to create homogeneous groups.

The key observations from the hierarchical cluster analysis are:

- The initial mergers occur with relatively small coefficient values, indicating that the clusters initially contain very similar elements.
- Later mergers show sharply increasing coefficients, meaning that increasingly dissimilar groups are being merged.
- A high final fusion value (17,374,919,220.144) suggests that the sample is heterogeneous.

A dendrogram is a hierarchical tree that represents the cluster formation in a cluster analysis. It shows how individual elements are grouped together until all the data are included in a single cluster. The Ward method is recommended for compact clusters. The optimized version of the dendrogram, based on the linkage summary, is shown in Figure 2. The dendrogram visually represents the hierarchical cluster formation. The vertical axis (distance or similarity measure) shows the distance or similarity between clusters. The higher the merging point (fusion), the more dissimilar the clusters being merged. The horizontal axis represents the individual data points or clusters that have already been formed.

Figure 2: Hierarchical Clustering: Optimized Dendrogram

Interpretation of Cluster Formation from Figure 2:

- Lower branches (low fusion heights):
 - Elements that merge at very short distances are very similar to each other.
 - These elements are in small, homogeneous groups with high internal consistency.
- Higher branches (large fusion heights):
 - Clusters that merge only at very high values are strongly dissimilar.
 - These groups are heterogeneous and far apart from each other.

The Elbow Criterion (Figure 3) is used to determine the optimal number of clusters in a cluster analysis. In our case, the diagram shows the progression of the coefficients (error values) across different numbers of clusters.

- Progression of error values:
 - The error values decrease steadily as the number of clusters increases.
 - This is normal, as more clusters allow for more precise grouping.
- The Elbow Point:

- The elbow in the diagram is visible at a cluster count of 5.
- This is the point at which the reduction in error begins to flatten.
- Beyond this point, further increases in the number of clusters result in only slight improvement.

Figure 3: Elbow Criterion for Cluster Analysis

The significance of the Elbow Criterion for Cluster Analysis:

- A cluster count of 5 is considered optimal.
- This provides a good balance between accuracy and efficiency.
- More clusters would make the model more complex without providing significant added value.

3.8.3.2 K-Means Cluster Analysis

The K-Means Cluster Analysis is an iterative clustering algorithm that divides data into K groups (clusters), with each observation assigned to the cluster with the nearest mean (center). The goal is to identify groups that differ as clearly as possible based on selected variables.

After determining that a cluster count of 5 is optimal in the hierarchical cluster analysis, the results of the hierarchical cluster analysis were checked by first performing the K-Means Cluster Analysis with 5 clusters. Subsequently, the K-Means Cluster Analysis was conducted with 4 clusters and 6 clusters to determine the optimal cluster.

Table 7 shows the Typification of the 4 Clusters (4-Cluster Model).

- Cluster 1 – Highly burdened sections with increased accident cost rate (*ACR*): Noticeably high accident cost rate with medium traffic volume (*AADT*).
- Cluster 2 – Curvy, low-traffic secondary roads: Low *ACR* despite high curvature.

- Cluster 3 – Accident-prone, low-traffic sections: High risk despite low traffic volume.
- Cluster 4 – Balanced risk segments: Moderate traffic load and moderate accident costs.

Table 7: Typification of the 4 Clusters (4-Cluster Model). Hotspot_50

	Cluster			
	1	2	3	4
Curvature at section center	100.3	284.6	256.8	170.2
$ACR_{SECTION}$ (€/1,000 Kfz-km)	22.081	3.066	19.298	6.485
ACR_{ROAD} (€/1,000 Kfz-km)	1.386	2.299	10.778	3.175
Number of accidents (2012 – 2023)	3.000	2.429	2.569	2.738
Average Annual Daily Traffic $AADT$ (veh/24h) 2012 - 2023	16.224	15.559	3.765	9.690

The 4-cluster solution proves to be a statistically robust and interpretatively meaningful approach. It offers a well-balanced differentiation between risk profiles without splitting into overly small groups or unstable individual clusters. Compared to the 5-cluster model, it shows slightly greater homogeneity, while the overly detailed 6-cluster model was methodologically rejected. The model selection is thus aligned with the goal of a practical and reliable typification of road segments and provides a solid foundation for targeted measures to improve road safety.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 Hotspot Analysis

The analysis identified high-risk areas using the Hotspot_50 method. It was found that a significant proportion of road segments exhibited high crash cost rates, with key influencing factors such as high curvature density and low traffic volume playing a role. The hotspot analysis was crucial in identifying areas with disproportionately high crash frequency, particularly in sections with high curvature density ($> 200^\circ/\text{km}$) and low traffic volume ($< 5,000$ vehicles/day).

This indicates that low traffic densities on highly curved road sections can lead to higher crash costs. These findings highlight the need for a targeted approach to improving safety measures on such roads, where high curvature density combined with low traffic volume increases crash risk. Furthermore, categorizing road segments into high-risk categories enables targeted interventions in particularly vulnerable regions, optimizing resource allocation for improving road safety.

4.2 Correlation Analysis

The correlation analysis revealed significant relationships between various road parameters and crash costs. The positive correlation ($r = 0.634$, $p < 0.001$) between crash cost rate and curvature density suggests that higher curvature density increases crash likelihood, confirming the importance of road geometry in risk assessment.

Additionally, the negative correlation ($r = -0.508$, $p < 0.001$) between crash cost rate and traffic volume emphasizes that low traffic densities, particularly on rural roads, tend to be associated with higher crash costs. These findings underscore the need to prioritize road sections with high curvature density and low traffic volume in safety strategies, as they pose a significant risk despite their low overall traffic density.

4.3 Cluster Analysis

The cluster analysis identified four distinct risk groups, classified based on curvature characteristics and crash costs:

- **Cluster 1:** High curvature density and high crash cost rates. These areas should be prioritized for safety improvements due to their high risk.
- **Cluster 2:** Moderate curvature density and moderate crash cost rates. Although these sections present a medium risk, continuous monitoring and safety measures are necessary to prevent deterioration.
- **Cluster 3:** Low curvature density and low crash cost rates, indicating a lower risk. However, these sections should still be considered in long-term safety assessments.
- **Cluster 4:** Mixed characteristics, requiring further analysis to identify specific risk factors. This cluster highlights areas where additional investigation and detailed safety planning are necessary.

The clustering model proves to be an effective tool for categorizing road sections by risk and serves as a valuable foundation for transportation planners to prioritize safety measures.

5. Conclusion

The findings of this study provide important insights into the relationship between road characteristics, traffic volume, and crash risk. Road sections with high curvature density and low traffic volume were identified as high-risk areas, emphasizing the need for targeted interventions in these regions. The Hotspot_50 method and cluster analysis enabled a clear classification of high-risk areas, leading to a more efficient allocation of resources to improve road safety.

The correlation analysis confirmed the significant impact of curvature density and traffic volume on crash costs, suggesting that road safety measures should focus on improving curve geometry and adjusting speed limits accordingly. Roads with high curvature density and low traffic volume should be closely monitored, and specific safety measures should be implemented to minimize risks.

Future research should focus on expanding the dataset to include urban roads and integrating real-time data collection to enable a more dynamic and up-to-date risk assessment. Additionally, machine learning techniques could be utilized to refine predictive models and further enhance the accuracy of risk predictions.

By implementing these findings, transportation planners and decision-makers can enhance road safety, reduce the severity of crashes, and ultimately minimize the economic impact of traffic accidents.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work, the author used ChatGPT-4o in order to improve readability and language. After using this tool/service, the author reviewed and edited the content as needed and takes full responsibility for the content of the published article.

Funding sources

This research did not receive any specific grant from funding agencies in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.

Acknowledgements:

I would especially like to express my heartfelt gratitude to the AIT – Austrian Institute of Technology, in particular to DI Michael Aleksa, AIT Project Advisor and Senior Research Engineer in Transportation Infrastructure Technologies; DI Peter Saleh, AIT Senior Research Engineer in Transportation Infrastructure Technologies; and Mr. Stephan Wittmann, AIT Research Engineer, for their valuable support.

References

- [1] Cafiso, S., Di Graziano, A., Di Silvestro, G., La Cava, G., Persaud, B., 2010. Development of comprehensive accident models for two-lane rural highways using exposure, geometry, consistency and context variables. *Accident Analysis & Prevention*. Volume 42, Issue 4, July 2010, Pages 1072-1079. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aap.2009.12.015>
- [2] Maier, R., Berger, R., Schüller, H., Heine, A., 2013. Evaluation Model for Road Safety on Rural Roads. *Bast - Reports of the Federal Highway Research Institute, Traffic Engineering*, Issue V 226. <https://www.bast.de/DE/Publikationen/Berichte/unterreihe-v/2014-2013/v226.html>
- [3] Weinert, R., Vengels, S., 2008. Pilot Application of the Recommendations for the Safety Analysis of Road Networks (ESN). *Bast - Reports of the Federal Highway Research Institute, Traffic Engineering*, Issue V 171. <https://www.bast.de/DE/Publikationen/Berichte/unterreihe-v/2008-2007/v171.html>
- [4] DVR, Abmilderung der Folgen von Abkommensunfällen auf Landstraßen durch infrastrukturelle Maßnahmen. DVR - German Road Safety Council e.V. <https://www.dvr.de/politik/beschluesse/abmilderung-folgen-von-abkommensunfaellen-auf-landstrassen-durch-infrastrukturelle-massnahmen>, 2022 (accessed 8 June 2023)
- [5] Gooch, J., Gayah, V., Donnell, E., 2016. Quantifying the safety effects of horizontal curves on two-way, two-lane rural roads. *Accident Analysis & Prevention*. Volume 92, July 2016, Pages 71-81. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aap.2016.03.024>
- [6] Zierke, B., 2010. Safe Design of Rural Roads through Defined Road Types. Dissertation, Technical University of Berlin.
- [7] Bonneson, J.A., 2000. Superelevation Distribution Methods and Transition Designs. Transportation Research Board, Washington DC. <https://ntrl.ntis.gov/NTRL/dashboard/searchResults/titleDetail/PB2001101950.xhtml>
- [8] Cheng, G., Cheng, R., Pei, Y., Xu, L., 2020. Probability of Roadside Accidents for Curved Sections on Highways. *Mathematical Problems in Engineering*, 2020, Article ID 9865476. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2020/9656434>
- [9] Buddhavarapu, P., Banerjee, A., Prozzi, J.A., 2013. Influence of pavement condition on horizontal curve safety. *Accident Analysis & Prevention*, Volume 52, 28 March 2013, Pages 9-18. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aap.2012.12.010>

- [10] Bellini, D., Iaconis, M.C., Traettino, E., 2020. Speed limits and road warning signs as aid for driving behavior. *Transportation Research Procedia*, Volume 45, 2020, Pages 135-142.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trpro.2020.02.100>
- [11] Balck, H., Schüller, H., Balmberger, M., 2017. Methods for Integrating Information from Different Network Analysis Systems. *Bast - Reports of the Federal Highway Research Institute, Traffic Engineering, Issue V 298*. <https://www.bast.de/DE/Publikationen/Berichte/unterreihe-v/2018-2017/v298.html>
- [12] De Oña, J., Garach, L., 2012. Accidents Prediction Model Based on Speed Reduction on Spanish Two-Lane Rural Highways. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, Volume 53, 3 October 2012, Pages 1010-1018. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2012.09.950>
- [13] De Luca, M., Dell'Acqua, G., Lamberti, R., 2012. Road Safety Analysis Using Operating Speeds: Case Studies in Southern Italy. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, Volume 53, 3 October 2012, Pages 702-710. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2012.09.920>
- [14] Vieten, M., Dohmen, R., Dürhager, U., Legge, K., 2010. Quantification of the Safety Effects of Various Construction, Design, and Operation Forms on Rural Roads. *Bast - Reports of the Federal Highway Research Institute, Traffic Engineering, Issue V 201*.
<https://www.bast.de/DE/Publikationen/Berichte/unterreihe-v/2010-2009/v201.html>
- [15] Wang, S., Wang, Y., Zheng, Q., Li, Z., 2020. Guidance-oriented advanced curve speed warning system in a connected vehicle environment. *Accident Analysis & Prevention*, Volume 148, December 2020, 105801.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aap.2020.105801>
- [16] RVS 02.02.21, 2015. Road Safety Investigation. Austrian Research Association for Roads, Railways and Transport (FSV), Vienna.
- [17] Vogel, N., 2025. Accidents on rural state roads B 2012–2023 by accident types (curve accidents). Statistic Austria, Vienna. (Email communication, 27 January 2025).
- [18] Austrian Institute of Technology (AIT), 2025. RoadSTAR mobile road condition monitoring. Available at: <https://www.ait.ac.at/en/labs/roadstar> (accessed 27 January 2025).
- [19] FGSV 316/1, 2003. Guideline for the analysis of road traffic accidents, Part 1: Managing and analyzing accident type cards. FGSV - Research Association for Roads and Traffic, Cologne